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ABO blood groups and breast cancer

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Abstract

Background: Blood group A of the ABO system has been reported to be associated with some Malignancies including breast cancer (Ca).However, reports of the association of breast cancer Ca with various blood group have been conflicting.

Aim of the study: The aim of this paper is to study the association of breast cancer Ca with various blood groups

Patients and methods: Reviewing the case reports of 395 female patient with histopathological diagnosis of breast Ca whom were observed at the general surgery and oncology units at the University hospital in Al Kadhimiyia and the Nursing house hospital at Baghdad from the period from January 1990 to October 1997.Their ages ranged from 24-83 years (50.97+/- 12.6).400 females patients with disease other than malignancy were considered a comparative control.

Results: The distribution of blood groups in patients with breast Ca Table(1) was significantly different from the control group (Chi-square 9.6,Odd difference 3 P < 0.05).In patients with

breast Ca there was a higher prevalence of blood group O than the control group with a significant Chi-square (13.6),(P 0.05) for patients 50 years old and younger(Premenapause).Patients older than 50 years (Postmenapouse) showed higher prevalence of group B.Familial breast Ca occurred in the premenopauposal group

Introduction

Blood group A of the ABO system has been reported to be associated with some Malignancies including GIT malignancies,prostate,cervix,ovary,and breast malignancy [1,2] .Reports of the association of breast Ca with various blood group have been conflicting. George & Chalestry (1969) reported a significant predominance of blood group A in breast cancer patients [3].Moural et al 1980 &Levin et al1981 [4, 5] reported that 50 patients with progressive form of breast Ca have blood group A.

Tryggvadottir et al [6] in 1988 reported familial cases have 2 fold prevalence of group B. While the predominance of blood group O has been reported by Newell et al [2].

The association of breast Ca and blood group could have a role in identifying women at risk of developing breast Ca [1].

Patients and methods

Reviewing the case reports of 395 female patient with histopathological diagnosis of breast Ca whom were observed at the general surgery and oncology units at the University hospital in Al Kadhimiyia and the Nursing house hospital at Baghdad from the period from January 1990 to October 1997. Their ages ranged from 24-83 years (50.97 \pm 12.6). 400 females patients with disease other than malignancy were considered a comparative control. Their ages ranged from 20 to 82 years (49.3 \pm 13.7).

Family history: 123 patients (31.6%) have family history of breast Ca affecting first or second degree relatives. 255 patients (64.5%) didn't have family history of breast cancer. While in 17 patients (4.4%) the family history couldn't be determined. More than two third of the patients 83 (67.47%) with positive family history were under the age of 50.

116 (29.4%) patients have no clinical or histological lymph node involvement (stage -1) with 76 patients (65.5%) was under the age of 50 years.

Histopathology: 334 patients with breast cancer (84.6%) have invasive ductal

carcinoma (ductal type) including 9 patients with carcinoma in situ and 4 with Pagets disease, 60 patients (15.2 %) have lobular carcinoma, and one patients with cystosarcoma phylloides. 68.6% have moderately differentiating carcinoma.

Results

The distribution of blood groups in patients with breast Ca Table(1) was significantly different from the control group (Chi-square 9.6, Odd difference 3 $P < 0.05$). In patients with breast Ca there was a higher prevalence of blood group O than the control group with a significant Chi-square (13.6), ($P < 0.05$) for patients 50 years old and younger (Premenopause). Patients older than 50 years (Postmenopause) showed higher prevalence of group B. Familial breast Ca occurred in the premenopausal group. The ABO blood groups of patients with familial breast Ca were statistically different (Chi-square 27.2, $P < 0.05$, Odd ratio 3) from the non-familial cases table (1). There was no association between the histopathological type or the stage of the disease (lymph node involvement) any and specific blood group Table (2). Only 2 patients have bilateral involvement including 2 patients with poorly differentiated invasive Ca associated with AB and, A blood groups respectively. 87 patients have Ca on the left side including 3 patients with fibroadenoma on the right side, 2 of them have blood group B and one has blood group O.

Blood Group	Breast CA patients	≤<50 years	>50 years	Familial	Non-familial	Control group
A	98 (24.8%)	56(23.8%)	42(26.2%)	23(18.7%)	70(27.5%)	106(26.5%)
B	124(31.4%)	63(26.8%)	61(38%)	58(47.2 %.)	61(23.9%)	106(26.5%)
O	145(36.7%)	103(43.8%)	42(26.2%)	36(29.3%)	104(40.8%)	134(33.5%)
AB	28(7.1%)	13(5.5%)	15(9.3%)	6(4.8%)	20(7.8%)	54(13.5%)
Total	395(100%)	235(100%)	160(100%)	123(100%)	255(100%)	400(100%)

Table (1): Distribution of blood groups in patients with breast CA and the controls

Blood group	Histopathology		Stage (1)	LN involvement (+)
	Ductal	Lobular		
A	78(26. %) 11(18.3%)		31(26.7%)	67(24%)
B	104(31%)	19(31.7%)	33(28.4%)	91(36.2%)
O	118(35%)	27(45%)	48(41.3)	97(34.7%)
AB	25(7.5%)	3 (5%)	4 (3.4%)	24(8.6%)
Total	334	60	116	279

Table (2): Distribution of blood groups in patients with breast CA according to the histopathological types and lymph node (LN) involvement

Discussion

The age difference of the distribution of blood groups in this study agrees with finding of Anderson DE 1971[7], although he reported his observations on familial breast Ca and considered 45 years is the menopausal age. However our finding of higher incidence of blood group B in postmenopausal women contradicts the finding of Anderson of group A higher incidence in this group. However such difference could be attributed to the differing prevalence of

blood groups in different communities. In contrast to the observation of George P, Chalestry LJ of higher prevalence of group A among breast Ca patients, our patients have higher prevalence of blood groups B and O. The higher prevalence of blood group B in this study agrees with observation of Tryggvadottir L et al [6], who reported 2 fold higher prevalence of blood group B in familial breast Ca compared with the sporadic cases.

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